

The Bias in Population Survey-Based Migration Estimates

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Abstract

We prove that migration flow estimates from population surveys can lead to mistaken inferences. While estimates of individual and total flows are unbiased, most small flows are not sampled. This can lead to biased inferences about the patterns of flows. The problem arises from the framing error inherent in this enterprise. The sample frame is the whole population, while the proper frame to estimate migration flows is migrants. A survey designed for the former frame will fail to produce accurate results for the latter. The only exception to this occurs when all flows are large relative to populations as occur in state-to-state flows. In this case, each flow is large enough relative to the population that the probability that it is not sampled is vanishingly small.

1 Introduction

The subject of migration flows is of interest to many practitioners of demography and economics. We examine whether a population survey like the American Community Survey (ACS) is an effective means to estimate county-to-county migration flows. We construct models of migration flow sampling to answer this. Our findings are negative: most flows are not sampled due to framing error. The proper frame is the set of migrants, while the sample frame is the set of household residents. While the survey estimates of migration are unbiased, the missing flows can create a distorted picture of migration. This can lead to incorrect inferences about the patterns. Models using survey estimates of migration can be damaged by the missing flows.

2 Details

Let M_{ijt} be the migration flow from area i to area j during the period beginning at time t . In the case of interest, the areas are counties and the survey is the American Community Survey or a similar population survey. Theorem 1 shows that the probability of sampling a migrant in a flow increases with the number of migrants in that flow.

Theorem 1. *Given a constant sampling probability p , $0 < p < 1$, independent sampling of migrants, and a set of migration flows M_{ijt} , the probability that a flow is sampled increases in the size of the flow.*

Proof. Given that any migration flow M_{ijt} contains m_{ijt} migrants, the probability of sampling at least one of these migrants is $1 - \prod_{k=1}^{m_{ijt}} (1 - p) = 1 - (1 - p)^{m_{ijt}}$. This is an increasing function of m_{ijt} ; thus, the claim is proved. \square

Theorem 1 assumes that individual migrants are sampled independently. In practice, the ACS samples households independently. Then, all individuals are sampled within a household. Thus, individual migrants are sampled with unequal probabilities. However, due to the similarity in the distributions of migrant household sizes, the variation in individuals' probabilities of sampling is small for all practical purposes. Therefore, Theorem 1 holds as a first-order approximation for individual migrants.

Consider a flow of 10 migrants in the ACS. By design, $p \approx .025$. The probability that the flow is sampled is $1 - (1 - .025)^{10} \approx 0.22$. About 80% of migrant flows, being less than 10, have even smaller

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probabilities of being sampled. This means that ACS and similar surveys will not survey a large proportion of these flows, as in the 2006-2010 ACS 5-year estimates (Esther Miller, personal correspondence.) While estimates of individual flows and the flows are unbiased, inference about migration patterns will be biased towards larger flows, possibly creating a distorted view of migration. Only if all migration flows are large enough to be sampled like state-to-state migration flows, $1 - (1 - p)^{m_{ijt}} \approx 0$, like state-to-state migration flows, does this distortion go away.

An additional complication is that the nonrandom missingness pattern of the flows can harm models that use them as inputs. To some extent, this can be mitigated by imputation. However, the risk that the unsampled flows systematically vary from the sampled ones remains. Thus, more comprehensive datasets like IRS personal income tax records should be used as inputs, with adjustments as necessary for compatibility with the data being modeled. The IRS data contain for each household with taxpayer, the counties at which the residents live. The data can be linked by householder or person to provide migration estimates for every county-to-county flow. While the data have their biases, these can be largely remedied by using supplemental data including survey data.

3 Conclusions

The framing error in surveys like the American Community Survey make them poor sources of migration estimates except for areas with large population. While the migration estimates are unbiased, small ones like most county-to-county flows are generally missed. More comprehensive migration estimates can be obtained from data like the IRS personal income tax data. Most importantly, these data approximate the sample frame of all migrants.